

PSYCHOSEXUAL DISORDER AND EDUCATIONAL DYSFUNCTION OF SCHOOL

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Abstract:

The paper discuss the issue of sexuality education from different aspects related to: (a) importance and possibility of incorporation of sexuality education into regular school curriculum, (b) possible transfer of experiances of good praticies (such as programme School Without Violence) into sexuality education curriculum, (c) school institutional readiness to respond to the challenge and obligation of introducing sexsuality education into school curriculum, and (d) possible consequences if the society and school does not accept this curricula intervention.

Key words: education, sexuality education, School Without Violence, educational dysfunction

INTRODUCTION

Many global socio-political-economic trends in Europe, such as economic crises and falling GDP due to the Corona 19 pandemic, years of strengthening populist, nationalist and conservative political parties and declining standards of human rights and freedoms, are likely to affect that the sexuality education in a number of countries, including Serbia, will remain one of the biggest controversies and challenges for the school in the coming decades in the 21st century. Every time the question of the importance and role of sexuality education as a school subject (and content) is raised in the public in Serbia, these controversies open in an almost traumatic way. Is the sexuality education and in what way part of the answer to the question what kind of school we need in the future? Whose and what are those arguments the key in the discussion on this topic? Who should decide on that and in what way? Is the status of sexuality education in schools in Serbia the result of some general public consensus; the result of agreement between the profession, science, the lay-public and the executive and legislative (educational) authorities?

A large number of topics, challenges and almost everyday problems that parents and teachers have are related to the psychosexual development of children and youth. Given that every person's psychosexual development begins at birth, that sexuality is an integral part of every person and the core of the construction of integrity and identity, and that psychophysical and sexual changes occur throughout life, it is clear that parents, educators and teachers face a huge responsibility and a serious task - how to provide a child with a healthy psychosexual growth and a stable, strong, positive and balanced identity and integrity for the whole life. A happy, fulfilled and safe childhood is an inexhaustible source of positive life energy.

The knowledge that during the development of awareness of sexuality the child socializes, but also through all other processes of socialization

the child acquires awareness of the uniqueness of its own personality and builds the experience of its own sexuality, clearly indicates that the psychosexual development of every child is most strongly connected with every part of everyday process of learning, work and life of the child in school. At no time sexuality does develop separately from all other developmental (physical, emotional, intellectual and social) processes of the child (Weisner 2011). The complexity of each child's sexuality expression stems from the connection that sexuality has with all physical, emotional, intellectual, and social needs, abilities, and experiences. Also with attitudes (e.g. about gender, morals, aesthetics, law, freedom...). The experience of sexuality is the experience of one's own personality and these things cannot be separated (Andjelković & Weisner 1997).

The usual behavior that educators and teachers notice is that pre-school children play „doctor“, „husband and wife“, are interested in the genitals of other children, second grade students hold hands as an act of expressing sympathy, in the third grade they exchange love letters and boys in fourth grade behind school buildings leaf through pornographic magazines. The fact is that, contrary to stereotypical understanding, „Sexuality is not something that suddenly enters the lives of young people when they become sexually active...“ (Weisner 2011, 157).

THE IMPORTANCE OF SEXUALITY EDUCATION

Everything that makes the most intense psychosexual development of each person and secondary sexual characteristics (muscle growth, erections, menarche...), accompanied by changes in behavior, usually happens at the age of 10 to 18, i.e. during adolescence and obligatory regular schooling. Universal knowledge is that the period of early adolescence is also

characterized by weak influences and connections with parents, and stronger resistance to authority, identification with peers and willingness to freely experiment and face risks.

The natural interest of children and young people in their own and other people's sexuality and its expression is most often condemned by adults and followed by educational measures such as prohibitions, threats, incitement to fear and prejudice, causing feelings of guilt... At the same time, one of the most significant, increasingly present health risks for children and young people is premature interpersonal sexual activity of young people. All research, from any country, confirms that young people have their first experiences of interpersonal sexual activity at a younger age (much earlier than their parents), but also that many children cannot speak openly and freely about sexuality and their risky behavior, neither at home, nor in the wider community. Many parents are not sure how to provide their child with a sexuality education, fearing an open and intimate relationship and changes in the relationship of authority and family values, or simply do not have the necessary knowledge. That is why most often parents only reproduce and convey to their children the views represented by other most important factors of socialization and creators of public discourses - the media, the church, school and representatives of state institutions.

Risky sexual behavior of children and young people is very often accompanied by other health risks (use of cigarettes, alcohol and drugs, non-compliance with traffic regulations, challenging games...). Short-term illnesses and easily healing unwanted injuries are not the only consequences. The consequences for health and life in such situations can be far more severe (self-harm, trauma, disability...) or the most severe, such as loss of life. The age limit when young people become sexually active has been declining in Serbia for decades. The median age of first sexual intercourse among young people in Serbia aged 15–19 is 16, and the percentage of

young people aged 15 – 19 who had sexual intercourse in 2009, compared to 2000, increased by 10.4%. (Knežević, Simić & Ivanović 2009). At the same time, according to the data from 2000 (compared to 2009), there is no significant difference in the regular use of condoms by young people. (Knežević, Simić & Ivanović 2009).

Experiences of the first interpersonal sexual activities are almost always the causes of some of the strongest stresses, frustrations, fears and conflicts in adolescence, because they are often accompanied by various negative influences of peers and streets: persuasion and pressure, extortion and threats, alcohol and drug abuse... Such examples are typical for all social groups/networks and are regularly reflected in all spheres of creativity: play, sports, learning, socializing... Unfortunately, a huge part of the population of children and youth do not have the right support, care and education about these changes, both in the family and at school, regardless of the fact that these psychophysical changes are one of the most important things for children and youth. In fact, they are very often exposed to violence.

According to the data in the Situational Analysis of Children and Adolescents in Serbia (UNICEF in Serbia 2019), and based on data from the records of the social protection system (2013–2017) and the Republic Institute for Social Protection from 2017, the number of families in which children were victims of violence in 2013 amounted 3,637, in 2015 – 6,520, and in 2017 – 8,297. Gender-based violence is widespread in families and schools: 69 percent of elementary school students and 74 percent of high school students in 2015 stated that they were exposed to at least one form of gender-based violence. The perception of social distance presented in the same publication, based on the report of the Commissioner for the Protection of Equality from 2016, shows that by far the largest social distance in Serbia exists towards minority sexual orientations and identities (far greater than any other ethnic, religious... stigmatized population).

SCHOOL WITHOUT VIOLENCE AND ITS SEXUALITY EDUCATION PROJECT (1994 – 2004)

In 1994, the „School Without Violence“ program was launched, as a long-term program of peace education and prevention of violence against children and youth and among children and youth. The program was created as a project of the Peace Movement Pančevo. The goal of the „School Without Violence“ was (a) Protection of children and youth from all forms of violence (direct, structural and cultural) and creating a safe environment for their development, (b) Realization and encouragement of all developmental (physical, emotional, intellectual and social)) potentials and needs of children and youth, (c) Development of competencies of those who work professionally with children (teachers, pedagogues, psychologists, social workers...) and parents, and (d) Development of a culture of peace and tolerance. The author of the „School Without Violence“, Aleksandar Weisner (author of the paper), had the need and motive to start such a program in the direct experience of working at the school as a teacher, but also as the founder member of the Peace Movement Pančevo (1991). The „School Without Violence“ program was a response to the problem of the war in Yugoslavia, but also the indoctrination and institutional violence that existed in schools.

One of the key long-term projects of the „School Without Violence“ was about sexuality education. The sexuality education project was intended for children and youth, teachers, parents and members of professional and other non-governmental civil society organizations. That is why the way of realization was multimedia, multidisciplinary and multisectoral. Activities began in June 1997 with the printing and promotion of the „It's Easy“ manual. The content of the manual includes workshops on sexuality education for primary school teachers and parents. This manual with 198 pages of interactive material and theoretical material was published with the support of Inge

Project from Darmstadt and Janja Beč. Until 2004, as a sexuality education activity of the „School Without Violence“ program, numerous workshops, seminars, lectures, presentations, debates and tribunals were organized in Pančevo. For example, in his several visits to the „School Without Violence“, the psychologist Leo Lensing, the family-therapist in the counseling office of Pro Familia (Konstanz, Germany), held lectures and workshops to the group of teachers of elementary and high schools, pedagogues and psychologists. L. Lensing demonstrated some of the methods, techniques and skills. As part of the presentation of the sexual education programme in Germany, teacher Ingrid Maurer (Meersburg, Germany) was talking about her experiences of working in elementary schools. That part of the program was developed with the help of peace organisation Friedensinitiative Konstanz. For a group of about 30 young members of JAZAS (Yugoslav's association against AIDS) 8 workshops on sexuality education were realized (education of high schools peer educators). The workshop leaders were psychologist Vanja Kunovac and Aleksandar Weisner. In cooperation with Youth Center in Pančevo it was organised workshop titled „How to positively experience oneself and others“ for secondary school pupils. During open-public discussion „Sexual education in schools – pro at contra“ in Youth Center, the participants (pupils, parents, teachers, psychologist and medical practitioners) were debating and exchanging arguments why sexual education should be or should not be a school curriculum. The debate was held with 80 participants. In some more activities, the representatives of the Association of the Educational Workers, Forum of the High School Pupils, Society of Teachers of Pančevo, Association of Psychologists and Pedagogues of Pančevo and Center for Social Work were participated as well. In meantime, many teachers started to implement and practice with their pupils the workshops and techniques they were experienced and learned participating in the project „School Without Violence“. Hundreds of copies of the manual „It's Easy“ were distributed, primarily to teachers and parents who participated at seminars and workshops, but also to civil society organizations dealing with education and care for children and youth, in Serbia and in Montenegro, Croatia and Slovenia.

PRINCIPLES AND METHODOLOGY OF THE SCHOOL WITHOUT VIOLENCE

The sexuality education project of the „School Without Violence“ was created with the conviction that young people learn about sexuality and sexual health from many different, more or less reliable sources. However, the basic premise of the program was that school should play a central role in this process. The whole idea was based on the principles and attitudes of Nikola Potkonjak and Petar Šimleša they outline in *Pedagoška enciklopedija*: „In fulfilling its task of educating young people with healthy mental and moral qualities, able to harmonize their relationships with the community, and thus build a personal life worthy of a man, the school must not miss sexuality, as a natural phenomenon, and gender relations. Children should be systematically informed and taught about sexuality“ (Pedagoška enciklopedija 1989, 378).

During the numerous realized activities of the project, examples were given of the introduction of sexuality education as a subject in schools in Sweden and Germany in the 1970s, and their results were presented in response to common prejudices about sexuality education that children, encouraged by conversations about sex, engage in experimentation and sexual intercourse earlier. The project also promoted studies from various countries that show that quality sexuality education reduces the likelihood that young people will unpreparedly step in sexual activities, and that, if they are already sexually active, they will be more responsible and use adequate protection. Those studies also contained the belief and confirmation that education about psychosexual development and sexual relations will significantly reduce the feeling of anxiety of children and young people. Also, participants in the program activities were reminded that research in Serbia confirms that young people are particularly exposed to sexually transmitted diseases, that the number of unplanned and unwanted pregnancies is high and worry-

ing. Yet, more than teaching about medical and biological content, the program was designed as a human rights-based and gender-focused approach to sexuality education. The main intention was to support development of constructive communication and adequate response to decision-making challenges as a part of negotiation and risk-reduction skills. In situations where young people are faced with challenges and needs, exposed to various peer pressures and many other different types of violence, the strongest, healthy and constructive stronghold is their personal social skills and integrity in decision-making. The program stayed always focused on personal development and education for human rights and prevention of discrimination and other violence, especially in formal education, contributing to better relationships among peers, parents, teachers and sexual (present and future) partners: „Perhaps even more than the lack of timely information on the anatomy and physiology related to sex, the psychosexual development of children and youth is harmfully affected by the huge dehumanization of relations between the subjects of the teaching process, and the humanization of these relations will. [...] Every sexuality education aims at the emancipation of the personality, the affirmative realization of all developmental potentials - physical, emotional, intellectual and social. It should contribute to the development of the most important categories of life in all participants in the educational process: emotional stability and fulfillment, complete and positive experience of one's own personality, mature and responsible attitude towards problems, better understanding of the needs of others, tolerance and solidarity. [...] The degree of healthy growing up of children, as a basis for their successful and happy life, depends on how much teachers and parents will accept children's sexuality as normal and healthy and to what extent they will succeed in developing pupil's knowledge and a healthy experience of sexual intercourse“ (Andjelković, Weisner 1997, 11–12). In that way, the project implemented a holistic view of sexuality, sexual behaviour and sexuality education, going beyond the traditional focus on prevention of pregnancy and sexual transmissive disease by including an emphasis on psychosocial aspects of the sexuality education as a curriculum. That was re-

ally helpful in responding to the wider sociocultural determinants of sexual practice and attitudes.

The criteria for the implementation of various activities of the project have always been that the work with different participants must take place in a safe social environment and with an age-appropriate context and contents. Lectures, workshops and presentations, studies of foreign professional literature and debates... have been realised by instructionally sound teaching methods that actively involved the participants with the respect of need for a holistic and multi-sector approach. The „School Without Violence” program has always strongly supported the belief that by „implementing a sexuality education project, teachers, pedagogues and psychologists help children to develop knowledge, skills and experience:

- At the field of health: on the development of healthy habits in sexual relations, maintaining one's own psychophysical health, on the prevention of sexually transmitted diseases and unwanted pregnancies, on a critical attitude towards the use of alcohol and drugs;
- At the psychological level: establishing personal identity and integrity, reducing feelings of anxiety, greater self-confidence and security, assertiveness, satisfying curiosity, neutralizing and amortizing psychological pressures;
- At the social level: on quality communication, negotiation skills, healthy interpersonal relationships, better understanding of the needs and feelings of others, relationships unencumbered by prejudice and discrimination, on relationships of trust, opportunities for counseling, on gender equality;
- At the cognitive level: on recognizing risky forms of behavior, knowledge on psychophysical changes during adolescence, information on rights and obligations, on recognizing and eliminating techniques of gender domination and discrimination, on sexually transmitted diseases and prevention of diseases, on opportunities for psychosocial support and assistance;

- At the creative level: on the development and realization of creative potentials, on creative techniques of personal expression, creative problem solving, on the importance of insight into different approaches to events“ (Weisner 2011, 161).

„School Without Violence“ advocated and promoted sexuality education as part of the basic rights of children. The rights enshrined in the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child directly relate to the need and obligation to introduce sexuality education because the rights set out in the Convention include the right to protection from harmful effects to development, the right to protection from sexual exploitation and other forms of exploitation, the right to education, health care and social care, the right to freedom of expression and participation in decision-making concerning their well-being, the right to participate in family, cultural and social life, and the right to protection against discrimination on any grounds.

After ten years of successful implementation of the program, in 2004 the author, Aleksandar Weisner, and associate of the program, Maja Gargenta, expecting support for further development of the program, handed over to the UNICEF office in Belgrade (coordinator Svetlana Marojević) the complete program „School Without Violence“, with all projects, including a project on sexuality education, four manuals printed within the Library „School Without Violence“ (including the manual „It’s Easy“), research and evaluation results and press-clipping.

Unfortunately, after that, UNICEF, illegally, violating copyright and abusing the program, started activities presenting the program „School Without Violence“ as its own, without any consultations, consent or communication with the author of the program or the organization Movement for Peace Pančevo. In doing so, the biggest abuse was committed against the program and program beneficiaries, as UNICEF reduced activities on the peer violence project, ignoring the importance of sexuality education and prevention of institutional violence against children and youth. In this way, UNICEF caused enormous damage to the further development of sexuality education, but also to the „School Without Violence“ program as a whole.

None of the later attempts to implement sexuality education (e. g., a pilot project „Health Education on Reproductive Health“ 2012–2015 of Provincial Secretary for Sport and Youth of the Autonomous Province of Vojvodina in partnership with Institute of Public Health of Vojvodina, or „Educational Package” of Incest Trauma Center in partnership with Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development Republic of Serbia 2016– 2017), no matter they were in cooperation with the ministry or the initiative of the state administration, it did not have a comprehensive approach, quality of content, principles and methodological approach and results as the „School Without Violence“ program, nor did it last that long. Unlike these programs, which were accompanied by various controversies due to which they were suspended, during the seven years (1997–2004), as long as the various activities of sexuality education „School Without Violence“ lasted, there was no case of problematic event, conflict or incident, although all activities were organized and implemented in public, with media coverage (radio, magazines, TV), and the total number of participants of very different ages and profiles (children, youth, parents, teachers, health workers, psychologists, social workers, members of various organizations...) during those years could be measured in hundreds.

In 2006 the World Health Organization did promote „Defining Sexual Health. Report of a Technical Consultation on Sexual Health“. In 2009, UNESCO published the „International Technical Guidance on Sexuality Education“ (in further text ITGSE). „Standards for Sexuality Education in Europe“ (WHO Regional Office for Europe, the Federal Centre for Health Education and the European Expert Group on Sexuality Education) were published at 2010. All of this publications and many more respective educational materials are bringing explanations on quality standards and methodological instruction, and presenting the comprehensive sexuality education (in further text CSE) as necessary approach, means that understanding of the sexual health requires a positive and respectful approach to sexuality and sexual relationships (WHO 2006). Also, sexuality education requires social

contextualised, age-appropriate, evidence-informed and interactive education approach for teachers, health educators, parents and pupils/students. One of critical characteristics of CSE curricula, recommended by the ITGSE, is the examination of gender inequalities, gender norms and power in relationships. Important school-based program recommendations and lessons learned, presented in the Review of the Evidence on Sexuality Educationis, are augmented with community components or services, such as training for health providers, youth-friendly services, and work with parents.

By evaluating the sexuality education program of the „School Without Violence“ it is easy to recognise that all of the mention recommendations were systemic implemented and were integrative elements. Additional quality of the program came from the basic approach, since that, according to Haberland, N. & Rogow, D. insight, there are still, on international level, very few CSE programmes that explicitly address empowerment or gender equality in a meaningful way (Haberland, Rogow 2015). Even, some other researchers did find very few systematic reviews reporting on studies that involved violence prevention as components or key characteristics (Montgomery & Knerr 2018), which makes the significance of the sexuality education project of the „School Without Violence“ even more important, in the international and theoretical context.

LESSONS LEARNED

Sexuality is a fundamental aspect of human life and it has physical, psychological, spiritual, social, economic, political and cultural dimensions (UNFPA, WHO & UNESCO, 2009). But sexuality education, in many societies, still raises many political and social questions, beyond the health and educational issues. In that way, sexuality education is a controversial and contested issue that has evoked wide debate on its aims, contents, methods,

pedagogy and desired outcomes. The majority of studies demonstrate the importance of understanding structural, socio-historical and cultural factors influencing sexuality education (Simovska Ros Kane 2015): „There is a need to better understand the perspective of children and young people and the potential for less conventional settings such as the Internet, social and other media as well as peers, for learning and competence development related to sexuality. School-based sexual education needs to reconnect with these tendencies, rethink and redefine its aims, modes of delivery and pedagogical approaches if it is to play a meaningful role in children and young people’s learning and competence development related to sexuality, sexual rights and related social justice.“ (Simovska Ros Kane 2015, 5).

One of the most frequently used arguments against sexuality education is that it precipitates an earlier onset of sexual relations among youth. The second most frequent argument is assessment that parents should be those responsible for teaching their children about their sexuality, not the school. At the same time, systematic reviews of any programme worldwide shows that there is strong evidence that sexuality education programmes did not have negative effects, based on knowledge of The United Nations Population Fund, UNESCO and WHO. On the contrary. Studies in several European countries have shown that the introduction of long-term national sexuality education programmes has led to a reduction in teenage pregnancies and abortions and a decline in rates of sexually transmitted infections (STI) and HIV infection among young people aged 15–24 years (Sexuality Education 2016). Research studies in Finland (Tanton, Jones, Macdowell et al. 2015) and Estonia (Haldre, Part & Ketting 2012) shown that good quality sexuality education does not lead to young people having sex earlier than is expected based on the national average. Actually, good quality sexuality education can lead to later sexual debut and more responsible sexual behaviour (Apter 2011; Van Keulen, Hofstetter & Peters 2015).

There are many more researches concluding the very similar, such the research conducted in Britain which showed that persons who learned

about sexuality matters at school, experienced first sexual intercourse at a later age than those who got their information from other sources such as friends or the media, rarely have been diagnosed with a sexually transmitted infection and young women being better protected from sex against their will. (Macdowall, Jones, Tanton et al. 2015).

UNFPA, WHO and Federal Centre for Health Education recorded some more, so called „soft“ outcomes of good quality sexuality education: awareness of human rights, acceptance, tolerance and empathy for others, gender equality, confidence and self-esteem, empowerment and solidarity, critical thinking, skills in negotiation, decision-making and assertiveness, mutually respectful relationships... (Sexuality Education 2016). Also, the International Planned Parenthood Federation indicate that sex-positive approaches acknowledge and tackle the various concerns and risks associated with sexuality, without reinforcing fear, shame or taboo of young people's sexuality or gender inequality (IPPF 2011).

Research „Sexuality Education in Europe“ has shown that what is needed or necessary, as integral part of the programme, is guidance on the emotional and social aspects of sexual relationships. This is the reason why the title of the subject in some countries (Belgium, Cyprus, Britain...) is „Relationship and Sexuality Education“. The review also found that there is strong international evidence that school-based sexuality education has a positive effect on knowledge and awareness of risk, values and attitudes, efficacy to negotiate to use condoms, and communication with partners and parents (Sexuality Education in Europe 2006).

„Sexuality Education in Europe and Central Asia“ is report and overview of 25 countries from Western Europe, Eastern Europe and Central Asia (WHO European Region) and presents an assessment of the status of sexuality education conducted at the end of 2016 and in early 2017. This overview reports about „remarkable progress“ which has been made in the European Region in developing and integrating sexuality education curricula

in formal school setting and can be concluded that school sexuality education is now „the rule“ in the European Region. For example, in 2017 in the UK it was decided that sexuality education must be taught in all schools of the country, both, public and private. This report provides folder evidence clearly indicates that early onset of sexual contacts is not the result of sexuality education, supported by documents explaining that the two countries with the lowest percentage of young people that already had started sexual contact at age 15 (the Netherlands and Switzerland) have had comprehensive sexuality education program for many decades. Also, in countries that have fully developed and comprehensive program, use of contraception trends to be high among young people, and teenage birth rates tend to be very low. Conversely, high teenage birth rates are found in all countries where sexuality education is underdeveloped on or none exist (Ketting & Ivanova 2018).

THE CASE OF SERBIA

The same report the status of the sexuality education in Serbia described as still in an early stage of development and that only very few elements are included in biology courses, and, since that there is strong opposition to sexuality education in Serbia, only very few sexualityeducation topics are included in biology classes, and these are strictly limited to body awareness and reproductive functions. Even, this biology chapter comprises six teaching hours. “There is serious opposition to sexuality education in Serbia, mainly from the Ministry of Education, teachers and other school staff as well as parents. The main arguments against it are related to the presumed ‘inappropriateness’ of the topics for youth. An important political concern related to reproductive health in general concerns the governmental objective to increase the (low) birth rate, and as a result addressing issues like gender equality, prevention of unwanted pregnancies and STI’s (sexual transmitted infection), the right to choose an sexual orientation

are not seen as necessary, let alone desirable“ are standing in the report (Ketting & Ivanova 2018, 144).

These problems were also pointed out by the „School Without Violence“ back in 1997, comparing and giving a critical analysis of the change in curricula for the courses „Knowledge of Nature“ and „Biology“ in primary school, because all contents on reproductive organs and a whole chapter on contraception were expelled from the textbook. What was new in relation to the 1988 Biology textbook is the text that the renewal of the population in many parts of Serbia is at a worryingly low level, that this phenomenon threatens the survival of „our nation“, that it should be understood that the future of the nation rests on numerous youth and that each individual must be aware of responsibility for the future of the nation (Andjelković & Weisner 1997).

WHAT CAN WE EXPECT FROM SOCIETIES THAT OPPOSE TO SEXUALITY EDUCATION?

Omission, pressures and punishments, not only hinder the proper development of personal sexuality, but also the mental health of adults and negatively affect their acceptance of sexuality and its experience (Jovanović & Jovanović 1991). Knowledge from sexology is increasing, and the age limits for entering into sexual relations and expressing risky behavior are decreasing. It is important to mention the problem of low health culture and communication culture, the problem of gender discrimination, a high degree of sexual abuse of children... For all these problems, sexuality education is an important answer.

Contradictory attitudes towards the sexual behavior of men and women are widespread in society. Gender discrimination, which unfortu-

nately existing as a value and social capital, is part of these contradictory relationships. In relation to the path of personal development, the roots of this discrimination are found in common or very similar patterns of socialization characteristic of the family, school, church and *mass*-media. In all these environmental factors, the elements of machoism and misogyny are most often clearly visible, directly based on traditionally developed patriarchal stereotypes and roles assigned on the basis of biological differences. As such, they are contrary to the ideas of basic human rights and freedoms.

Because of all the above, it is easy to conclude that societies, that resist sexuality education, and schools, which ignore psychosexual development, needs and problems of children and youth, are very engaged and systematically working to deprive children of knowledge, experience, attitudes and skills on how to: to develop a positive experience of themselves and others, to have a healthy attitude towards their own sexuality, to develop tolerance, understanding and respect in relation to others, to be responsible in a partnership, to develop habits and styles of healthy living and to protect themselves from various diseases, to protect themselves from sexual violence and various forms of discrimination... That is, such an attitude of society and school actively contributes to the problems of low health culture and culture of interpersonal relations, the problem of gender discrimination, a high degree of sexual abuse of children, endangering children's health... This is not just the opposite of what the goals and tasks of the school are and the violating rights of children, but can cause serious psychophysical and emotional harm to children and youth, their creative and social skills and social relationships, but also to a safe, happy and fulfilled growing. Such a specific relationship, practice and the role, make the school psychosexually disorder and educationally dysfunctional, since that has affect on the mental and emotional experience of sexuality, causing difficulties in adjusting to a normal lifestyle and has in general negative consequences for pupils and society.

CONCLUSION

One of the necessary changes in the school in Serbia, which causes anxiety and fear among the professional and resistance in the general public, is the introduction of sexuality education as a teaching content or curriculum. Sexuality education is the most important way to support children and young people in their sexual and overall development and one of the crucial factors in protecting their health and well-being. The school in Serbia persistently and for a long time resists all these facts, ignores the results of the research and behaves contrary to the legal obligations and rights of children and youth. It is the neglect of children and young people. It is a matter of mass, generally accepted, ubiquitous, meaning systemic and systematic institutional violence that is supported by almost the entire educational profession and that causes huge harm to children, youth and the whole society. The absence of critical thinking and the tendency to conformist behavior of the profession – teachers, pedagogues and psychologists, makes the problem especially difficult.

Sexuality education is a fundamental social determinant of a healthy society, and the unwillingness, incompetence and fear of teachers must not be an argument for the non-existence of this content in schools. In case of Serbia, psychosexual disorder and the educational dysfunction of the school in relation to the sexuality education of children and young people is a consequence of the cumulative effect of unprofessional and illegal behavior of the UNICEF office and the Ministry of Education and their favoring of traditionalist discriminatory practices and populist political organizations.

Extremely rare are quality initiatives, alternative programs and models that give formal education a chance to reject wrong and, above all, harmful pedagogical practices for children, and set a good example for development and quality improvement. „School Without Violence“ was such an example in Serbia.

Can anyone today punish pupils by whipping him with a stick on their palms, forcing him to kneel in the corner of the classroom... and to consider it as an appropriate pedagogical measure? Does any teacher today force a left-handed kid to move a pencil from left to right and write with his/her right hand, because it is unacceptable for a teacher's professional and methodological knowledge for a pupil to write with his left hand? Are there still teachers who order all students in the classroom to keep their hands behind their backs and sit still while the teacher teaches *ex catedra*? Does the school today have the right to reject children with developmental problems? Such and similar pedagogical practice has become a thing of the past because it is not admissible and is harmful? Today's professional and lay-public can be ashamed and condemned that it used to be the usual behavior of schools. But it is still not the past that the school systematically and systematically deprives children of knowledge about their development, health protection, violence prevention and gender equality. Today's professional and lay-public can be ashamed and condemned that it used to be the usual behavior of schools. But it is still not the past that the school systematically and systematically deprives children of knowledge about their development, health protection, violence prevention, rights and gender equality, while cultivating discriminative practices. In the same way, in the future, teachers, pedagogues, psychologists, parents, employees of the Ministry of Education, as well as all other responsible and serious adults whose duty is to help children and young people realize all their development potentials and provide them with quality education and safe conditions in school, condemn today's school behavior in relation to sexuality education. Many countries have completed this process.

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PSIHOSEKSUALNI POREMEĆAJ I OBRAZOVNA DISFUNKCIJA ŠKOLE

Rezime:

U radu se razmatraju teme o seksualnom obrazovanju iz različitih aspekata u vezi sa pitanjima o: (a) važnosti i mogućnosti uvođenja seksualnog obrazovanja u regularan školski plan i program rada, (b) mogućnosti transfera iskustva i znanja iz primera dobre prakse (kao što je program „Škola bez nasilja“) u nastavni plan i program seksualnog obrazovanja,

(c) spremnosti škola i obrazovnog sistema da odgovore na izazove i obavezu uvođenja seksualnog obrazovanja u nastavni program, i (d) tome koje su moguće posledice ukoliko društvo i škola ne prihvate seksualno obrazovanje.

Ključne reči: obrazovanje, seksualno obrazovanje, Škola bez nasilja, obrazovna disfunkcija

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